

Natalia ROȘCA

gr. did. I, Liceul Teoretic Orizont din Chișinău

Teaching Vocabulary as an Aspect of English Language Training

Abstract: *The article argues that the choice of vocabulary-teaching methods and activities depends both on the teacher's own didactic style and on the envisaged type of activity. Also, the choice of an activity or a particular method ought to be made depending on the students' needs so as to turn it into the best approach. The methods presented in the article are all student-oriented and all of them are motivating,*

student-engaging, practical, and aiming at improving students' language skills. Some important rules for teachers while introducing new vocabulary in a language class are also put forward.

Keywords: *teaching vocabulary, translation method, direct method, student-oriented teaching, individual work, group work.*

Rezumat: *Articolul aduce argumente în favoarea faptului că alegerea metodelor și a activităților de predare a vocabularului depinde, în egală măsură, de stilul de predare al profesorului și de tipul activității vizate. De asemenea, selectarea unei activități sau a unei metode specifice de predare trebuie să se realizeze în funcție de necesitățile elevilor, astfel încât să se aleagă abordarea optimă a acestui aspect. Metodele prezentate în articol sunt orientate spre elev/student, fiind motivaționale, captivante și practice, și având ca scop îmbunătățirea abilităților de vorbire. În acest context, articolul scoate în evidență și unele reguli importante pentru profesor în prezentarea vocabularului nou în timpul unei lecții de limbă străină.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *predarea vocabularului, metoda traducerii, metoda directă, predare orientată spre elev/student, lucru individual, lucru în grup.*

More important than the curriculum is the question of the methods of teaching and the spirit in which the teaching is given.

Bertrand Russell

No one will dispute the fact that teaching English in modern schools has by now overstepped traditional limits. It is not teaching English for the sake of English, but studying it as a source of communication and exchange of information. The amount of information and new knowledge may seem quite overwhelming for modern learners. The necessity for getting more and more knowledge increases tremendously, and as an inevitable consequence, the role of the English language grows, bringing a greater need for new language-teaching methods.

It is the teacher's aim and purpose to create an atmosphere of encouragement and willingness in their classroom, so that each student will want to make an effort, not just the more successful ones. Every pupil should be made to participate during each lesson in order to mobilize the whole class.

When teaching English, the emphasis is on teaching pupils to communicate. Thus, the main objective is to create true life situations in which the pupils can interact in pairs, in groups, in triads and in the class as a whole. For this purpose, the learners ought to be motivated and

feel involved in their own learning, an attitude that will generate a need and a desire to study a foreign language.

What does it mean to know and to use a word? Which words do learners need to learn and how will they learn them? These questions reflect the current focus on learner needs in the acquisition of lexical competence and the role of teachers in guiding them towards this aim. Teachers have never doubted the value of learning vocabulary. They know how communication grinds to a halt when learners lack the necessary word units. Vocabulary plays a crucial role in peoples' lives and their future possibilities. A rich, well-developed vocabulary is the hallmark of an educated individual, and indeed, a large vocabulary repertoire facilitates the development of an educated person to the extent that vocabulary knowledge is strongly related to literacy in particular and school achievement in general. To know a language means to master its structure and words. Thus, vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language that needs to be taught in school.

The aspect of teaching vocabulary

The problem is deciding which words and idioms the pupils need to memorize. It is evident that the number of words should depend on the number of hours/lessons that learners have per week. The scientific principles of

selecting vocabulary should be [2, p. 182]:

- frequently used;
- usefulness (easily combined);
- range – unlimited from the point of view of style (oral, written);
- included in the topics the syllabus sets;
- valuable from the point of view of word-building;
- key words, ensuring a good comprehension of the context.

The other principles are of didactic value; they serve teaching aims. The selected words may be grouped under the following two classes:

1) *Structural words* – words we talk with and make the structure of the language;

2) *Content words* – words that we talk about.

Both of these groups are of great importance. The selection of the vocabulary, although important, is not the teacher's main concern. It is only the "what" of teaching and it is usually prescribed for the teacher by the textbooks and the study-guides that are used. The teacher's concern is "how" to get the students to assimilate the vocabulary prescribed. In this respect a number of rules for teachers may be distinguished [2, p. 179]:

- 1) While teaching vocabulary, introduce the words in sentence patterns in various communication situations. Present the words in keeping with the structures to be taught;
- 2) Present the word first as an element of a sentence pattern. Then fix it in the pupils' memory through various exercises involving sentence patterns and phrase patterns;
- 3) When introducing a word, put it in context, then ask the pupils to pronounce it both on its own and in context;
- 4) In teaching words it is necessary to establish a memory bond between the new word and those already covered.

HOW TO TEACH VOCABULARY

There are two methods of conveying the meaning of words: **the direct method**, also called **the natural method** [1, p.53], and **the translation method**. There are different techniques for the use of **the direct method**. It is possible to group the words into *visual-based* and *verbal-based*. The first group involves the use of visual aids to convey the meaning of unfamiliar words. These may be objects or pictures showing objects or situations. The teacher may also use movements and gestures to help the students understand the meaning of the new words. The second group of techniques involves the use of verbal means for conveying the meaning of unfamiliar words. The teacher may rely on context, synonyms, antonyms, definitions, word-building elements etc.

It is difficult to cover all the techniques a teacher may

have at their disposal in order to convey the meaning of new words directly, without the help of the students' mother tongue. However, the use of the direct method is restricted. Whenever the teacher needs to present words denoting abstract concepts, they ought to resort to the mother tongue.

The translation method may be applied in two variants:

- 1) Common (proper) translation;
- 2) Translation-interpretation.

This method is efficient for presenting new words, because it is time-saving and ensures the exact comprehension of the meaning of the words presented.

METHODS OF TEACHING VOCABULARY

In my continuous teaching practice I have developed a number of materials (charts, schemes, cards, flashcards, posters, worksheets, Microsoft Power Point presentations etc.) taking into account the four levels of speaking abilities: beginning, pre-intermediate, intermediate, and upper-intermediate, or advanced. All levels depend heavily on the teacher's encouragement and help with mastering the vocabulary. The proposed methods may be applied at all four levels, provided they are adapted adequately so as to meet the class requirements in learning. They work best when the pupils have already acquired a certain amount of words in English and are able to put them in practice – that is to say, from the 3rd grade up.

VOCABULARY CARDS – the aim is to keep track of one's own words. I bring a stack of index cards.

- 1) Give several index cards to each student. They will be expected to provide their own from this point on.
- 2) Students write each word on one side of the card.
- 3) On the reverse they write anything to help them remember the word – it may be a translation or a mnemonic – and a sentence (of their own composition) with the word.
- 4) During the lesson the students sometimes flip through the cards to see how well they remember the words.
- 5) The students assess each other's knowledge of the words in pairs.
- 6) When the students are sure that they know certain words, they ask a partner to quiz them and, if they truly know these words, the index cards are discarded.
- 7) Encourage the students to keep their cards handy in a purse or in a pocket so as to review them at every opportunity.

WORKING WITH WORDS

I write on the blackboard a list of words that the students have already been exposed to through a recently

studied text. Then I write the definitions in a jumbled order in a different place on the board. Make up a set of sentences in which each word from the list has been left as a blank. For example, if one of my words were *clown*, I would write: *In the circus, a..... makes people laugh.*

- 1) I give the students a choice of four tasks:
 - they may write sentences that include the words, preferably two of the words in each sentence;
 - they may match the word and its definitions;
 - they may find the text through which they learned these words and copy the sentence where the words appeared;
 - they can listen to me or to another student read the sentences where words fit in the blanks and write the sentences including the missing words.
- 2) The students who finish one task in the given time can go on to another task.
- 3) Assess the execution of all the tasks with the whole class. Make sure to listen to several of the original sentences.

THE VOCABULARY HOUSE

I have a list of words that I want to review on the board.

1. Students draw a floor plan of the house, apartment, or room where they currently live.
2. The students' task is to write as many words from the list onto places in their house, to know and to be able to explain why they have put each word in this particular place.
3. Give them an example by saying something like: *Oh, here is the word "frustrated". I would put the word "frustrated" in the kitchen, because I hate to cook and I always feel frustrated when I try.*
4. Students stand and mingle. They meet classmates and tell them where they placed one of their words and why. Then they move on to another classmate and repeat.
5. Continue as long as the interest is high. Note that the students may keep their "vocabulary houses" in the classroom and keep adding new words as we go along.

THE MISSING WORD

I choose eight and ten words that I want to review, and write each word on a large index card.

1. In small groups, students review the meaning and spelling of the words.
2. Each group gives itself a name.
3. Write their names on the board.
4. Line up the index cards in a visible place in front of the classroom.
5. Appoint a scorekeeper.
6. Each group sends a representative to the front.
7. The group representatives study the card lineup.

8. They turn their back to the cards.
9. Remove one card and rearrange the card order.
10. The students in front turn to look at the cards.
11. The first student to shout out the missing word scores a point for their group.
12. New group representatives come to the front and the activity is repeated as long as interest is high.

ALPHABET SHOPPING

1. I review all the words connected to, for example, food. Let the class contribute with words they might have picked up in places other than the classroom. Put all the new words on the board. Allow some time for studying, then erase.
2. In small groups, the students go through the alphabet, trying to contribute the names of as many food items as possible for each letter.
3. I stop the activity when I notice that most groups have done about all they can.
4. The first group presents all its contributions under A. When an item is mentioned, it is crossed off everyone else's lists.
5. The next group gives the B's. Continue throughout the alphabet. The group that has items no one has mentioned is the winner.

We can do the same activity with a variety of vocabulary categories – clothes, furniture, animals etc.

WORDS TO MAKE A CAKE

1. Together with the class elicit all the words that describe the ingredients of a cake (flour, sugar, milk, eggs, butter, cocoa etc.). Write these words on the board as they come up.
2. Review all the verbs needed to describe cake making (mix, stir, add, scoop, pour, bake, fry, break etc.). Write these words on the board as they come up.
3. The students review the words in small groups.
4. When I am reasonably sure that everyone knows the words, I erase them from the board.
5. In small groups the students write a recipe for a special cake.
6. A representative of each group reads the recipe of the group.

We may, of course, vary this exercise to describe other actions, such as building a house, making a dress, giving directions etc.

VOCABULARY WALL

1. Assign one part of the classroom wall as "the vocabulary wall".
2. At the beginning of the lesson ask the students if there were any new words they didn't understand from the text.

3. One student takes the responsibility of writing these words clearly, in large letters – each word on a separate card or piece of paper.
4. Affix the words to the vocabulary wall.
5. Spend some time in each lesson reviewing the vocabulary wall: the students must know how to pronounce a word, how to spell it and how to use it in a sentence.
6. When everyone in class has truly and thoroughly learned the word, remove it from the vocabulary wall.

THE KWL ACTIVITY

On a large piece of paper, draw a three-column chart. On top of the first column write **KNOW**, **WANT TO KNOW** – on the top of the second column, and for the third column write **LEARNED**.

1. Write the necessary topic on the board.
2. In small groups the students pool their knowledge of the topic.
3. A representative for each group reports the group findings while either the teacher or a student summarizes the information and writes it in the **KNOW** column.
4. In small groups the students write questions they have about the topic.
5. A representative of each group reads out the questions while either the teacher or a student summarizes the questions and writes them in the **WANT TO KNOW** column.
6. Volunteers provide answers to any of the questions that have been asked and the student recorder puts these under the **LEARNED** heading.
7. As the study of the topic goes on, bring out the chart and complete the third column.

CONCLUSION

As I have mentioned before, vocabulary acquisition depends on the teacher's creativity, ingenuity, skill, and

perception, as well as their ability to choose the appropriate techniques and didactic strategies while taking into account the students' particularities. Therefore, the activities described in this article will differ when applied in specific learning contexts: for instance, lower grades will master their vocabulary through tongue twisters, riddles, poems, plays, short dialogues, games, sayings etc. Higher or senior grades will master vocabulary through Word Banks, Word Houses, making up sentences and then selecting the best ones for reading in class. In post-text activities the pupils may learn new words using dictionaries, including online ones. Commentary is a widespread technique to help master vocabulary units. It involves the sharing of ideas, predicting, finding out, imagining situations, recalling and applying knowledge, discussing and debating.

Each of the above-mentioned methods of introducing vocabulary has its role in class, aiming at arousing the students' interest and motivation for learning the given vocabulary, thus leading to further language structure acquisition and fluent speech development. Moreover, being given interesting methods and ways of acquiring new vocabulary, the students also get involved in finding solutions for issues, because they too feel that the activities are student-centered. Considering the most adequate and appropriate techniques during the classes, I keep in mind Ralph Waldo Emerson's saying: "Sowing an act, you'll reap a habit. Sowing a habit, you'll reap a character. Sowing a character, you'll reap a destiny".

REFERINȚE BIBLIOGRAFICE

1. Batool N. The Direct Method: a good start to teach oral language. In: *Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics*, Vol. 5, 2015.
2. Vizental A. *Metodica predării limbii engleze. Strategies of Teaching and Testing English as a Foreign Language*. Iași: Polirom, 2008. 336 p.
3. <https://www.onestopenglish.com>